

Centre for
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In Situ Micro-CT Imaging of Compression Loaded Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer Specimens with Voids and Wrinkles

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CFRP Yacht Masts

- CFRP yacht masts can be anywhere from a few metres in length to over 90 m in length!
- They can be much thicker than aerospace structures. Could be anywhere between 4 mm and 150 mm
- These structures are loaded primarily compression, but also undergo some bending and torsion
- The typical laminates used are highly directional and could be up to 70% of plies in 0° .

Largest carbon yacht masts

Source: https://cdn.boatinternational.com/bi_prd/bi/library_images/AB2t2OSLQBKhDnzQmZda_Magma-largest-masts-world-960x540.jpg

Small carbon sail boat

Source: http://www.finot.com/ecrits/ecritgroupe/confer_je/Dsc00053.jpg

CFRP D-Mast Using Female Moulds

- CFRP D-masts and wing masts may be manufactured using prepreg in two sections.
- The forward and aft sections are laid up and cured separately before being bonded together using a single lap joint.
- The corner areas of aft-mast sections have been found to contain wrinkles and voids.

Source:

https://www.cdk-technologies.com/files/images/Infrastructure%20CDK/_MG_0375.jpg

Cured Aft-Mast Section

Typical Defects in Curved CFRP Regions

Voids and porosity

- Porosity – generally used for smaller distributed voids
- Discrete voids – Larger more distinct voids which may contribute to failure initiation
- Bridging – usually cigar shaped voids occurring in corner regions

Fibre misalignment

- Waviness – in-plane to the plies. Usually caused method of transportation between supplier and manufacturer, or storage.
- Wrinkles – out-of-plane to the plies. Usually caused due to method of manufacturing. More likely in thicker parts and/or regions of high geometric variances (e.g. sharp corners).

Laminate Specification

- Unidirectional prepreg CFRP with Toray - T700 standard modulus carbon fibres and Hankuk – RS4545S resin system
- A female “U-shape” mould was constructed using aluminium with corner radii of 20 mm and sidewall angles of 100°
- During the lay-up process, the material was debulked after every third layer which is standard industry practice for these laminates.

Fibre orientation on laminates

- $[0/90/0/45/-45/0/-45/45/0/90/0/45/-45/0/-45/45/0/90/0/0/\pm 45]_S$
- 60 %, 30 % & 10 % of 0°, ±45° and 90° plies respectively, which is typical for CFRP yacht masts
- 0° plies lie along the length of the mast
- Corner regions are extracted from the aft-section for image analysis

Aluminium mould with 20 mm corner radius

X-Ray Micro-CT

- Void characterisation method to isolate and quantify size, shape, and location of voids established using adaptive thresholding and noise reduction techniques
- Orientation quantification methods were created using structure tensors and two dimensional discrete Fourier transform

Average aspect ratio of voids larger than 0.1 mm² for all three planes of analyses

- 18 specimens of various defect severities were scanned and analysed
- Longest, widest, thickest and largest (volumetric) voids were identified and quantified
- Aspect ratios of voids in each plane were calculated

Longest Void (x)*	> 20 mm	Maximum void count	62
Widest Void (y)	8.2 mm	Largest void volume (mm ³)	5.59
Thickest Void (z)	1.35 mm	Average void volume (mm ³)	0.12

*void extended beyond scan

Ring Artefact Reduction Method

- The technique assumes the centre of rotation of the CT scan to be the same location as the origin of a polar transformation of the reconstructed images

- Then any ring artefacts can be converted to vertical lines by converting the image from Cartesian to Polar coordinates

- Systematic changes which are similar and comparable to rows above and below are used to identify if the variation corresponds to a ring artefact

- A normalised correction of local greyscale pixel intensity is applied to any pixels identified as an artefact. This is based on local and global average pixel intensity of each 2D reconstructed slice

Ring Artefact Reduction Examples

The polar image is then converted back into Cartesian coordinates to provide a reduction in ring artefacts.

3 mm

Example 01

Example 02

Example 03

Example 04

3 mm

3D Visualisation – Ring Artefact Reduction and Void Extraction

High void content

Low void content

Part Quality Variation Along Mast Length

Three different qualities – same part

$x = 300 \text{ mm}$

$x = 450 \text{ mm}$

$x = 750 \text{ mm}$

Combined Loaded Compression (ASTM D6641)

- 9 specimens were tested at the Centre for Advanced Composite Materials (University of Auckland) using acoustic emission monitoring, high speed cameras and strain gauges.

- 9 specimens were tested at μ -VIS X-Ray Imaging Centre (University of Southampton) with a load cell and X-ray μ -CT scanning at 2 to 6 load intervals.

ASTM 6641 CLC – High Speed Cameras

- Failure modes - sublaminar buckling and compression fracture of fibres observed
- Compression failure is difficult to capture - occurs within 3 frames at acquisition rates of 20,000 FPS
- Large differences in failure strength between specimens, but less variation in overall specimen stiffnesses
- Overall void volume fractions showed an effect on final failure loads

High Speed Camera Results

Single camera test - four different time steps close to failure load of a specimen undergoing sublaminare buckling

Test with two cameras - four different time steps close to compressive failure load ("brooming")

Novel *in situ* X-ray μ -CT CLC Test Fixture

- Concept to prototype and testing
- Use of intermediate modulus CFRP load bearing structure used within imaging window to allow for adequate X-ray transparency

In-Situ μ -CT of CLC Tests – Specimen Centroid Alignment

Using Mean Intensity Projections to Identify Damage

Specimen 02 - P1_S01 @ x = 6.2 mm

in situ X-ray Micro-CT - Damage Behaviour

x
 z 1 kN 36 kN 38 kN 3 mm

Damage at three load steps
[Specimen 05 - P3_S02 @ $y = 3.8$ mm (top),
and @ $y = 10.1$ mm (bottom)]

- Surface fibre bundles buckling
- Final failure mode – “brooming” fibre breaking under compression acceptable in accordance with ASTM D6641M combined loaded compression test
- Interlaminar matrix shear cracks observed in some specimens

1 kN 38 kN 1 mm x z
Shear cracks in Specimen 05 caused by compression loading

in situ X-ray Micro-CT Results

- Total void volume fraction showed an effect on final compressive strength. Higher void content tends to decrease compressive strength.
- Magnitude of the largest dimension of the longest and widest voids showed to have an effect on compressive strength.
- Average void aspect ratios, such as width-to-thickness, showed an inverse relationship to compressive strengths. This was likely due to high aspect ratios being associated with smaller “needle” shaped voids

◆ ASTM 6641 CLC Test × in situ μ -CT Compression
 Linear (ASTM 6641 CLC Test) - - - Linear (in situ μ -CT Compression)

Conclusions

- Novel image processing techniques were developed to characterise defects using X-ray μ -CT scan data
- Large voids in curved CFRP parts are typically cigar or lens shaped, lie along the x-direction and appear to be caused by ply bridging.
- The mechanisms that cause defects to occur during manufacturing results in larger wrinkles and voids to be fairly interactive with each other. Large wrinkles were usually found to contain needle shaped voids adjacent to them.
- Various methods of ring artefact removal techniques were investigated. A suitable technique based on the balance between computational efficiency and quality of reconstructed images have been identified and applied to μ -CT scan data
- Microscopy is only a valid method of defect characterisation with very large numbers of samples from the same laminate as there is a significant variation in defects formed within the same laminate within a distance of ~ 100 mm.
- Some damage initiation occurred from void edges, but at up to 90% failure loads, minimal damage was observed in X-ray μ -CT scan data other than surface fibre bundles buckling and minor interlaminar shear cracks

Thank you *Questions?*

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